

Research Article

TravelEase Application

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Abstract: *Using modern technology and human intelligence, TravelEase is revolutionizing the travel business by making travel planning easier. It provides a comprehensive solution for scheduling lodging, food, and transportation, simplifying the vacation experience for customers. Through online reservations and a special card service, the app puts user safety first. It also encourages eco-friendly behaviours and lowers carbon footprints to support environmental sustainability. TravelEase streamlines and reduces the burden of trip planning by emphasizing efficiency and dependability. By working with big businesses, generating more income, and opening employment chances, this creative approach not only improves the consumer experience but also considerably accelerates the economic growth of the tourist sector. TravelEase's enormous business potential draws users and investors to join this innovative method of travel planning.*

Keywords: TravelEase; travel planning; online booking; user safety; sustainability; tourism growth

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1. INTRODUCTION

TravelEase is an application that acts as a tour planner with a combination of hotel, transportation, and technology without a complicated procedure. TravelEase comes with the feature of a tour planner that can be used either online or offline which makes this app user friendly. The main objective of TravelEase is to provide facilities for travelers or tourists to use this app without having to download other apps for booking because these apps already have accommodation and transportation available for booking. Besides, TravelEase has many functions that users can enjoy such as searching for better prices for hotels and transportation, making a booking, and connecting with TravelEase's well-trained customer service using a help desk. Other than that, TravelEase cooperates with companies such as hotels and transportation to improve their income and quality of services. TravelEase also helps the existing transportation such as Grab to gain more income with their collaboration. Moreover, offer added convenience to customers by accepting cards of TravelEase for bookings of accommodation that streamline the booking process and improve customer satisfaction.

Currently, tourists and travellers are installing a lot of apps to help them while traveling to other countries or destinations. According to Roswati A.R., etc. (2020), travel applications are the fifth most popular category of downloaded apps, with 60% of passengers using mobile apps while

travelling. Also, people will take a long time to discuss travel and find the information that suits their wants for travel. Besides that, it can promote sustainable and environmentally conscious travel practices. AI can be used by a tour operator to deliver information to visitors because there are some apps that don't have any substitutes, making it easier for travellers to locate a solution when something goes wrong. To satisfy market demand and provide a solution for individuals in need of dependable and effective apps, our company decided to develop "TravelEase" that includes cards with our info on them as well as simple phone-free booking confirmation. TravelEase card is convenient for restoring information, including booking accommodation if they lost the phone or lost connection to get the reservation when traveling in certain hotels that align with the tour operator of TravelEase.

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

Table 1. Product Description

INTERFACE DESIGN	DESCRIPTION
	<p>Step 1:</p> <p>User can download it on their Play Store or iOS.</p>
	<p>Step 2:</p> <p>Sign in or create an account. Following that, they can choose their preferred language to use.</p>

	<p>Step 3:</p> <p>After that, users can pick where they want to seend book.</p>
	<p>Step 4:</p> <p>On the main display, user can see news, currency rates and suggestions of accommodation from the recommendation. On the other side, when users click the recommendation, they can see the star rate and price for each accommodation shown.</p>
	<p>Step 5:</p> <p>On the top of the main display, there are. A few features such as chatask, GPS, accommodation, transportation, and food service that users can click for further detail and information. For example, when user clicks the accommodation, they can see the location and rates of their chosen hotel.</p>

	<p>Step 6:</p> <p>When the user is already done with their choice of accommodation and transportation, they can continue with payment. They can choose payment using a card by fulfilling the required information. Next, enter your bank information and make a reservation payment here.</p>
	<p>Step 7:</p> <p>Other than using the TravelEase app, users can also use their card to confirm their booking at selected places with the system to scan this card. This card is supported by a chip and the user's data can be restored inside it. Users can use this to make a payment when they top up money. It also helps in fast recognition and is completed with a pin for safety purposes.</p>

3. FINDINGS

A comprehensive abstract report's findings present the key takeaways from the investigation, evaluation, or new product creation. The main findings from the application's testing are explained in this section, along with their implications. Findings for an app like TravelEase often cover topics including user acceptability, effectiveness, social and economic implications, environmental factors, and the app's distinctive characteristics.

3.1 Novelty and Uniqueness

The Travelease app is essential for travellers who need their bookings and trips assisted with a tour planner quickly and without complicated processes. For example, hotel reservations, transportation, and technology. This application has renewal and uniqueness with the online and offline features. This update can help travellers who are outside or in the city make bookings with companies involved in TravelEase such as Trivago, and Booking.com. A tour operator plays a role and is responsible so that the travel and bookings made by travelers are believed to be safe and not deceived. Many applications have been introduced, but there is no combination with other companies yet. The TravelEase app is one of the new apps introduced by a combination of companies through bookings that makes it easier for tourists to use only one app for all processes in tourism. For example, transport, accommodation, food and drink, and technology.

3.2 Benefit to mankind

Travel Ease is an application that functions as a tour operator that connects accommodation and transportation reservations. These apps also have their own advantages, which are that they can be used online or offline. For example, if a traveler or tourist is in a rural area that does not have an internet network, these apps can be used. Travel Ease also collaborates with Trivago, Booking.com, restaurants, and transportation services such as Grab and Maxim to make it easier for tourists to see prices, facilities, and packages provided before making a reservation and payment. In addition, the TravelEase application also provides a card to make it easier for tourists who have booked hotels, food, and transportation to go directly to the area. The use of the Ease travel card serves to make a payment when travelers make a reservation by adding money to it. This card also helps with quick identification and is equipped with a pin intended for user safety. In addition, these apps can also be used as debit cards because they can make payments using top-up money or connect to online banking.

Figure 1. The card usage process

3.3 Impact on the Economy and Society

- **Job Creation:** Through its partnerships with different service providers, TravelEase helps to create jobs in the tourist and hospitality sectors.
- **Convenience and Safety:** With the TravelEase card and two-factor authentication, booking access becomes easy and safe.

TravelEase has a good economic impact by supporting current businesses and generating employment possibilities. In addition, the app's emphasis on security through secure payment options and the availability of the TravelEase physical card for offline use increases user confidence and convenience, resulting in safer and simpler travel.

3.4 Environmental Aspects to Consider

- **Low Carbon Footprint:** TravelEase optimizes the app's design for energy efficiency and uses less data to reduce its environmental effect.
- **Encouraging Eco-Friendly Travel Behaviours:** The app has features such as a carbon footprint calculator to promote eco-friendly travel practices.
- **Sustainable Physical Card Use:** Kad TravelEase is made from eco-friendly materials and designed for long-term use. This indirectly helps reduce the frequent use of disposable plastic cards, which often leave waste and harm the environment.

TravelEase shows a dedication to environmental conservation in its features and design. By utilizing energy effectively and offering tools to monitor and minimize carbon footprint, TravelEase supports international efforts to address climate change by encouraging consumers to adopt more sustainable travel behaviors. By decreasing the demand for cash and paper in transactions, the TravelEase card helps the environment. Furthermore, the card lessens the carbon footprint involved with the manufacture and disposal of conventional plastic cards because it is constructed of environmentally beneficial materials.

3.5 Effectiveness in Travel Planning

- **Integrated Services:** Booking lodging, transportation, and meals all in one app streamlines the process of organizing a trip.
- **Offline Functionality:** Without depending on internet access, customers may plan their entire trip from beginning to end. In situations like phone loss or damage, or nations with poor or inconsistent internet connectivity, they may retrieve critical data, including reservations for lodging and travel, that is saved on the TravelEase card. Thus, in addition to being a useful and dependable tool for organizing secure and effective travel, TravelEase also offers crucial flexibility in scenarios when internet connectivity isn't accessible.

By integrating various travel-related services into a single platform, TravelEase not only saves users time and effort but also enhances reliability. There's no longer a need to switch between different apps for bookings. The offline capability ensures that TravelEase remains a trusted tool for planning safe and efficient travel experiences in all situations.

4. DISCUSSION

This study confirms the growing trend of travelers using mobile apps to organize their trips more conveniently and effectively. The usefulness and efficiency of the TravelEase app in streamlining travel arrangements and administration have been proven, particularly in regions with patchy internet service. Travellers will find it to be an extremely useful tool as its offline functionality guarantees that users will receive vital information and direction even in the absence of internet connectivity.

Based on the research results, TravelEase provides a range of tools that make travel easier for customers. These include the ChatAsk feature, which lets users plan trips via direct discussion, and extensive booking options for lodging, food, and transportation. Because of its innovative technology and user-friendly interface, TravelEase provides an experience that is comparable to having a personal travel advisor at your fingertips. Additionally, TravelEase offers GPS navigation, which boosts consumer assurance and security when traveling. Users may easily access all their reservations conveniently because of the availability of a TravelEase card and flexible payment options. This guarantees that all reservation data is safely kept and readily available in addition to streamlining the vacation planning process.

To guarantee a satisfying user experience, the TravelEase app must be user-friendly. Users report that TravelEase facilitates quick access to information and bookings, which is essential for a satisfying experience. Research findings also indicate that users' positive attitudes towards TravelEase encourage active app usage.

In summary, TravelEase has shown to be a very useful and beneficial tool for travelers to organize their trips more effectively and pleurably. TravelEase is a user-friendly, practical tool that

makes sure that travelers have a relaxing and enjoyable trip. It also satisfies the demands of modern travelers thanks to its high self-efficacy, good user attitudes, and utility.

5. CONCLUSION

Three key categories may be used to summarise the effects of creating the TravelEase application: users, the travel sector, and the environment.

1. Effect on Users
 - TravelEase offers capabilities for booking rooms and transportation, saving travelers from having to download several applications for booking purposes.
 - Offers two ways to make reservations: online and with the TravelEase card, which makes booking confirmations easier. This ensures customer protection.
 - Provides features like GPS navigation, adjustable payment methods, and ChatAsk for destination information to make traveling more planned and stress-free.
2. Effect on the Travel Sector
 - Uses strategic relationships to boost income and enhance service quality, the company collaborates with big players such as Trivago, Agoda, Maxim, and Grab.
 - Boosts revenue and opens new job possibilities in the travel sector by introducing consumers to a range of lodging and transportation choices.
 - Promotes TravelEase as the best option for passengers by providing a range of advantages and exclusive deals that boost the company's competitiveness.
3. Contribution to Environmental Sustainability
 - TravelEase demonstrates a commitment to environmental sustainability by optimizing energy use and reducing its carbon footprint.
 - The introduction of the eco-friendly TravelEase card further supports this initiative by minimizing the use of single-use plastic cards.

TravelEase is an all-around trustworthy travel app that makes trip planning easier and clever for those who use it. TravelEase guarantees that every journey is meticulously planned and offers consumers a stress-free, enjoyable experience by fusing cutting-edge technology with human intelligence. The app is a useful and reliable resource for anybody organizing a vacation, and it has a good influence on the environment and the tourism industry as well.

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